

THE NEXUS BETWEEN BOARD ATTRIBUTES AND PROFITABILITY OF QUOTED MANUFACTURING COMPANIES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The research was set out to examine the nexus between Board attributes and profitability of quoted Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria. Specifically, the study looks into the effect of Board Gender, Board Committee, and Board Independence on profitability of manufacturing Companies in Nigeria. The study adopted the ex post facto research design and data was gotten from the financial statement of listed Manufacturing Firms. The study investigated sixty (60) listed Manufacturing Firms (Industrials, basic materials, consumer goods, oil and gas) for the period of 10 years 2013-2022. Panel least squares was used to estimate the models of the study. The findings of the study revealed that Board Committee has no significant impact on profitability of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria; It was also found that Board gender diversity (Female Directors) has a positive and significant effect on profitability of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria while Board Independence has a negative and significant effect on profitability of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study concludes that board attributes have an impact on the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study therefore recommends that the representation of Female directors and Board independent Directors be increased in manufacturing firms in Nigeria to enhance their profitability.*

Keywords: Board Attributes, Board committee, Board Gender, Board Independence, Manufacturing Firms.

INTRODUCTION

In the wake of the accounting scandals involving Enron and WorldCom, along with other financial crises, regulatory bodies have emphasized the necessity for a more diverse board of directors. This emphasis stems from the belief that a well-characterized board enhances decision-making processes within companies (Wang, 2018). A characterized board encompasses various elements, including its size, the delineation of responsibilities between the board chair and the CEO, as well as its overall composition and diversity. The board serves as the primary decision-making entity within the

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organization, prioritizing the protection and maximization of shareholder wealth. The concept of a firm's board is rooted in the attributes or incentive variables that play a crucial role in overseeing and controlling managerial actions, effectively acting as a conduit between company management and shareholders (Wetukha, 2020). Nwanne (2019) identifies board attributes such as board size, which refers to the total number of directors, the proportion of independent directors relative to the total board, and managerial ownership, which indicates the percentage of shares held by the CEO. Conversely, profitability is defined as the extent to which a business or activity generates financial gain, reflecting how effectively a company utilizes its assets to produce profit. Kajola (2019) describes it as the firm's capacity to leverage its assets for revenue generation. The achievement of optimal returns on assets through board activities is influenced by several factors, including the roles of executive directors, the contributions of independent non-executive directors, the presence of foreign directors, the impact of female directors, and the overall effectiveness of the board.

The board of directors, as the highest governing body of a company, bears the responsibility of generating profits. This entails that the board is actively engaged in the strategic development process and has unrestricted access to the necessary information to effectively fulfill its oversight responsibilities (Haris, Yao, Tariq, Javaid and Ul-Ain, 2019). Corporate board attributes refer to the characteristics and features of a company's board that facilitate the successful representation of the diverse interests of its stakeholders. The effectiveness of the board is assessed through both quantitative and qualitative measures. Quantitative factors include board shareholdings, gender diversity, size, independence, frequency of meetings, and the competence of board members.

The performance characteristics of board attributes have garnered significant attention worldwide, particularly in the wake of numerous corporate scandals and the failures of several prominent companies. The downfall of these organizations has underscored the inadequate role played by their boards, revealing deficiencies in corporate governance practices. Each series of corporate scandals over the years has reignited discussions surrounding corporate governance. For instance, the financial crisis in Asia in 1990 revealed vulnerabilities in checks and balances and governance practices, leading to the collapse of institutions such as Oceanic Bank, Intercontinental Bank, and Afribank, which subsequently shifted the focus towards insider trading. The subsequent wave of scandals at the beginning of the new millennium involved companies like Worldcom (USA), Enron (USA), Parmalat (Italy), and Air New Zealand (Australia). Research by Shetima (2019) indicates that the failures of these firms highlighted the shortcomings of governance processes, thereby intensifying the focus on board attributes and their composition.

In addition, increasing dissatisfaction among shareholders due to inadequate portability and declining share values has prompted inquiries into the competence of both the board and management. The remarkable growth demonstrated by corporate investors in various organizations has intensified scrutiny of corporate boards. These seasoned investors possess the necessary expertise to fulfill their

fiduciary duty of overseeing the board to ensure favorable returns (Watson, 2019). There is a growing acknowledgment that a thoughtful executive team serves as a valuable asset in various capacities, including fostering ventures, enhancing share development, and providing sustainable long-term returns for stakeholders (Ogbechie and Koufopoulos, 2019). Raheja (2019) notes that sound corporate practices are now recognized as a catalyst for economic growth. Amidst numerous corporate scandals, a common factor has been the ineffectiveness of boards of directors. This context underscores the necessity of conducting research to examine the relationship between board attributes and the profitability of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The aim of the research is to investigate the relationship between board characteristics and the profitability of publicly listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study will include:

- To examine the effect of board gender diversity (female directors) on profitability of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.
- To investigate the effect of board committee on profitability of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.
- To investigate the effect of board independence on profitability of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

H₀₁. Board gender diversity (female directors) has no significant effect on profitability of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

H₀₂. Board committee has no significant effect on profitability of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

H₀₃. Board independence has no significant effect on profitability of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Review

The discussion encompassed the concept of profitability along with the attributes of the Board as outlined below.

Profitability

Profitability, as defined by Okolie and Uwejajam (2022), refers to a firm's capacity to effectively utilize its resources to generate revenues that exceed its expenditures. In essence, a company is considered profitable when it achieves a net gain from its operations that surpasses its costs. This metric is crucial in the evaluation of financial statements, as well as in assessing overall company performance, effectiveness, and efficiency. Other important factors in this analysis include solvency and market potential. Jadah and Adzis (2018) emphasized that profitability represents the surplus remaining after

an organization has accounted for its expenses. Various indicators, such as net profit before tax, return on investment, return on capital employed, and earnings per share, are employed to gauge a firm's profitability. These metrics are vital for investors, creditors, and managers in determining a company's current standing and its future potential, provided that its operations are managed effectively. The two fundamental components of profitability are revenues and expenses. Revenues indicate the total income generated by a business, derived from sales of products or services, while expenses encompass all costs related to production—both direct and indirect—as well as selling and distribution costs. To achieve a high level of profitability, a business must efficiently utilize its resources to produce goods and services. Herbert (2018) noted that profitability is fundamentally concerned with the interplay between revenues and expenses, providing insight into a company's performance and its potential for future growth.

Return on Assets (ROA) is widely regarded as an effective internal management ratio for assessing performance, as it evaluates profit in relation to all assets utilized by an organization to generate those earnings (Oguda 2019). Consequently, it serves as a tool for analyzing the profitability, performance, and overall effectiveness of the organization. ROA offers valuable insights into a company's financial performance by illustrating how well assets are leveraged to produce income. It indicates the proportion of profit a corporation achieves relative to its total resources, thereby also serving as a measure of efficiency. As noted by Crownwell (2020), a high ROA signifies that a firm excels at converting its assets into profits. This ratio is typically viewed as a stable indicator of financial performance; an upward trend in ROA suggests enhanced profitability, while a downward trend indicates reduced profitability. n compared to its intended goals or outputs.

Concept of Board Attributes

The board consists of a collective of individuals who contribute their skills and expertise as social capital to the company, facilitating the execution of control and governance functions (Westphal, 2020). It holds the highest authority in decision-making and bears the primary responsibility for protecting and enhancing shareholder wealth. Additionally, the board monitors the firm's performance and evaluates managerial effectiveness. Nelson and Huse (2018) identified four key actions undertaken by the board during the decision-making process: initiation, ratification, implementation, and monitoring. Consequently, the board's principal responsibilities revolve around overseeing and approving decisions made by management. It ensures that the organization is free from detrimental management practices and actively works to prevent activities that could lead to corporate failures or scandals. Furthermore, the board is involved in all facets of management and financial oversight.

The board of directors plays a crucial role in an organization's performance and is integral to corporate governance, particularly concerning board characteristics such as size, diversity, committee structure, composition, meeting frequency, styles, structure, processes, activities, and interpersonal relationships. Jan and Sangmi (2019) examined the board's role in monitoring management actions, providing

consultative and supportive functions, and ensuring comprehensive governance by offering strategic direction to achieve organizational objectives. These essential functions serve as the basis for evaluating the effectiveness of most boards of directors.

Board attributes pertain to the characteristics that constitute a company's board of directors. According to John and Senbet (2018), three key features are essential for assessing the effectiveness of a company's board and its corporate governance: board size, board composition, and independence. The authors emphasize the importance of these attributes in improving board oversight and monitoring, which are crucial for achieving superior firm performance. Additionally, scholars such as Fauzi and Locke (2020) identify board diversity as a critical factor in evaluating a firm's corporate governance practices and board performance. In contrast, Ntim and Osei (2017) focus on the frequency of board meetings, while Klein (2020) highlights the significance of board committee structure in enhancing corporate governance effectiveness within firms.

Board attributes reflect and extend the characteristics of companies in fully addressing the interests of various stakeholders. The efficiency or effectiveness of a board is assessed through both quantitative and qualitative measures, including board independence, size, shareholdings, gender diversity, meeting frequency, and the competence of board members.

Components of Board Attributes

The components of board attributes considered in this study encompass the Board executive director, Board non-executive director, Board Diversity (specifically female directors), Board Committees, and Board independence.

Board Diversity (women directors)

The diversity of gender among board members is a significant aspect of board governance (Lukeman, 2018). This diversity is an important criterion in assessing the performance and effectiveness of the board. There is an increasing belief that female board members can enhance the board's overall effectiveness. Norway stands out as a pioneer in this area, having established a mandate that requires companies to ensure that at least 40% of their board members are women. Female directors are often perceived to contribute more effectively to the management of the firm through their expertise in areas such as law, human resource management, communication, and public relations compared to their male counterparts (Zelechowski and Bilimoria, 2020). Furthermore, Westphal (2018) notes that many prominent female and ethnically diverse directors come from non-business backgrounds, often rising to higher levels of directorship by demonstrating exceptional professional and institutional qualifications. This suggests that female and minority directors may not engage in the same networking systems as their peers, which are typically formed within their respective professional fields.

The Higgs Derek Report (2019) in the United States posited that diversity could enhance the effectiveness of corporate boards, highlighting the advantages that companies may gain from including professional women among their board members. The findings of Kastlungeret, Kun, and Clen (2018)

emphasized the presence of perfectionist feminine values in the context of tax-related matters. Conversely, Adams and Ferreira (2019) indicated that women tend to engage in rigorous oversight of managerial conduct and demonstrate a high attendance rate at meetings. Consistent with existing literature on gender disparities and tax compliance, Croson and Gneezy (2019) and Aliani et al. (2020) noted a negative correlation between gender diversity on boards and tax optimization strategies. The leadership styles of women and men exhibit distinct differences; women are often characterized by traits such as helpfulness, kindness, and sensitivity, whereas men frequently seek dominance in various situations (Eagly and Johannesen-Schmidt, 2019). These differences are also reflected in the composition of boards of directors concerning regulatory compliance. Edeh (2020) observed that women generally demonstrate a stronger alignment with compliance standards compared to their male counterparts. Furthermore, in relation to tax compliance, evidence suggests that women exhibit a more favorable attitude towards adherence to regulations than men.

Board Committee

An efficient board committee is evidently crucial for determining a firm's performance. This assertion is based on the understanding that the boardroom serves as the central hub or driving force of any organization, with decisions made by the board having a direct impact on the firm's outcomes. It is essential for each member of the board committees to regularly review financial reports, and all members are expected to avoid corrupt practices while demonstrating integrity and transparency in all committee affairs (Al-said, 2021). Board Committees not only provide a framework for organizational structure but also offer the necessary flexibility for the board to swiftly respond to the evolving demands of the environment (Edeh, 2020). The internal governance structure of the board significantly influences both its effectiveness and corporate governance practices.

In a study conducted by Klein (2018), the influence of board committee structures and the role of directors on board efficiency was assessed. The author advocates for a committee structure with clearly defined specialized roles that enhance productivity and oversight functions of the board. Additionally, King and Levine (2019) suggest that each committee should consist of qualified personnel, with the goals of each board committee focused on achieving the productivity and monitoring objectives of the organization. Commonly established committees within companies include those for finance, strategy, investment, audit, compensation, and nominations.

John and Senbet (2018) emphasize that committees focused on productivity, such as those dealing with finance, strategy, and investment, typically consist of internal members. In contrast, committees tasked with monitoring functions, including audit, compensation, and nomination, are generally made up of independent external directors. The authors found a favorable correlation between the presence of outside directors on monitoring committees and performance indicators associated with the advantages of monitoring, such as the firm's free cash flow and outstanding debt. Similarly, Bednar (2020) noted a positive correlation between the proportion of insiders on productivity committees and

performance metrics related to a firm's productivity, including stock market returns, net income, and capital expenditure efficiency.

Board independence

A board director is deemed independent when it is established that they possess no vested interests in the company or its management team (Arrondo, 2020). This indicates that the director does not serve as a consultant, external auditor, lawyer, or in any similar capacity. When an external director maintains independence from the firm, they are positioned to make informed and impartial decisions that can positively influence the organization's structure and operations.

Berghe and Baelden (2018) investigated the concepts of independence and board effectiveness by analyzing the monitoring and strategic functions of the board of directors. They concluded that the key to board independence lies in ensuring a sufficient number of independent directors are present. Their research highlighted that a director's capability, willingness, and the overall board environment can foster an independent mindset among directors. They assessed the performance of non-executive directors in China, finding that their objective and effective contributions to the board and the growth of firms are influenced by their independence, competence, access to information, and incentives. However, they also noted that the non-executive director system in China is weakened by excessive interference from controlling shareholders and a lack of understanding regarding the roles of non-executive directors.

Johari, Saleh, Jaffar, and Hassan (2018) noted that the current minimum requirement for independent directors is insufficient for effective management oversight. Additionally, Wooi and Ming (2019) highlighted that independent directors have not succeeded in fulfilling their internal monitoring responsibilities. The presence of independent directors can contribute a range of independent and objective perspectives, and a majority of them can help mitigate the risks associated with 'groupthink.'

Control Variable

In order to establish the true effect of the main variables in this study the researcher decided to introduce a control variable.

Leverage

According to Westphal (2019), firm leverage refers to the extent to which a company utilizes debt and preferred equity to finance its operations. A company that maintains a high level of financial leverage is likely to incur substantial interest payments. Leverage, often referred to as gearing, encompasses any strategy that involves the use of borrowed funds. When a company employs debt to acquire assets or to support a portion of its operations instead of relying solely on new equity, it is considered to be leveraging. While leveraging can amplify potential gains, it also has the capacity to magnify losses. Poor management of leverage can expose a firm to significant risks, particularly if financing costs surpass the asset's value or the income generated from it. The Dictionary of Business and Finance (2022) defines leverage as the utilization of debt financing and describes the leverage ratio as a metric that

assesses the relative contributions of stockholders and creditors, as well as the firm's capacity to meet its financing obligations. This definition confines leverage to debt financing, also known as financial leverage. Consequently, it is evident that firms with debt or any non-debt long-term liabilities in their financial framework are considered leveraged. As companies expand, the availability of investment opportunities increases, often outpacing the funds available from shareholders alone. This situation creates a demand for additional capital, prompting firms to seek external financing (financial leverage) or to draw from internal sources such as employees, retirees, or government entities (operating leverage).

Empirical Review:

Board diversity (Women directors) and Profitability

Evolutionary biology research suggests that women possess specialized skills tailored to meet the demands of nature. Consequently, there has been a discourse surrounding the essential traits women exhibit that are conducive to effective governance. It has been posited that women demonstrate qualities such as meticulousness, proficiency in financial management, risk aversion, and sound decision-making abilities (Azmi & Barrett, 2019). This has prompted several scholars to investigate the potential influence of female executives and board members on a firm's financial performance and market valuation. Research conducted by academics including Adams & Ferreira (2019), Campbell and Mingues-Vera (2018), and Farrell and Hersch (2016) indicates that female directors can positively affect both firm value and market capitalization. Additionally, Nielsen and Huse (2018) found that female directors contribute to reducing conflicts within corporate boards and engage in board development activities—such as work instructions, evaluations, and training programs—to enhance board effectiveness. However, empirical studies examining the correlation between female directors and a firm's financial performance yield inconsistent results. While some research highlights a positive correlation between women directors and financial value, other studies report no significant relationship or even a negative correlation.

Watson (2019) indicates that, after accounting for industry and firm age, there are no notable differences in performance between firms led by males and those led by females. Nevertheless, he also found some evidence suggesting that firms under female leadership might outperform their male counterparts. In a study utilizing Danish data, Rose (2017) concluded that there is no significant correlation between firm performance and the representation of women on boards. Conversely, Adams and Ferreira (2019) discovered that the average impact of female directors on firm performance is negative. This does not imply that the presence of women on boards lacks positive effects; rather, they may enhance financial performance in organizations characterized by weak corporate governance.

In a different context, Krishnan and Park (2019) investigated the relationship between female directors and return on total assets, utilizing data from the Fortune 1,000 database covering 679 companies. Their research revealed a positive correlation between the presence of women in management and

financial performance. Similarly, Carter, Simkins, and Simpson (2016) explored the link between Tobin's Q and the involvement of women on the boards of directors of Fortune 1,000 companies, uncovering a significant positive relationship. The results of these studies suggest that the inclusion of women on boards or in management teams may enhance overall performance by introducing diverse ideas and perspectives, ultimately leading to improved decision-making and outcomes.

Osemwegie and Ugbogbo (2019) conducted a study examining the relationship between board remuneration and diversity and the financial performance of publicly listed banks in Nigeria. The primary objective was to determine whether factors such as board remuneration and diversity—encompassing gender, ethnicity, nationality, and overall composition—affect financial performance. Financial performance was assessed through metrics such as return on assets (ROA) and share price (SP). The study analyzed a sample of fifteen (15) banks listed on the Nigerian Stock Group (NSG) over the period from 2009 to 2017. Various analytical methods, including Pearson correlation analysis, descriptive statistics, variable redundancy tests, and regression analysis, were employed to evaluate the data. The results indicated that board remuneration, gender diversity, ethnic diversity, and board composition positively influence financial performance, whereas diversity in nationality exhibited a negative impact. Consequently, the authors suggest that adequate remuneration for board members is essential, as it may mitigate conflicts of interest between board members and shareholders within the banks. Additionally, the study advocates for an emphasis on the qualifications of female directors on boards and recommends that listed banks strive to avoid the dominance of any single ethnic group among board members.

Eguasa and Amedu (2018) investigated the relationship between corporate attributes and firm performance in Nigeria. The study employed an ex-post facto research design and analyzed data comprising 110 observations from 22 Nigerian companies listed between 2012 and 2016. A simple random sampling technique was utilized, and the analysis was conducted using panel least squares regression. The findings revealed a negative and significant relationship between firm size and earnings per share. Consequently, the study recommends that companies prioritize the use of equity financing over debt.

Oyedokun (2019) explored the impact of board attributes on the value of listed commercial banks in Nigeria during the period from 2013 to 2017. This research also adopted an ex-post facto design, focusing on board characteristics such as gender diversity, size, independence, and frequency of meetings. Data were sourced from the financial reports of the listed commercial banks. The analysis was performed using multiple panel regression techniques. The results indicated that board characteristics significantly influence the firm value of these banks. Notably, gender diversity on the board had a positive significant effect, while the frequency of board meetings and certain board attributes exhibited negative significance. Additionally, board size was found to have a negative but insignificant effect, and board independence also showed an insignificant negative impact on firm

value. The study recommends that regulators and bank management in Nigeria should focus on optimizing board size and increasing the number of independent or non-executive directors with expertise in the financial services sector to enhance risk management and overall bank performance.

Board Committee and Profitability

In a similar vein, Al-Matari (2019) also established a positive relationship between the proportion of non-executive directors and return on assets. In the Nigerian context, additional studies corroborate this empirical evidence. For instance, Olayinka (2019) identified a positive relationship between board composition and corporate financial performance, specifically return on equity (ROE) and return on capital employed (ROCE), in a sample of 30 companies for the year 2017. Furthermore, Shehu and Musa (2022), analyzing a sample of 13 listed deposit money banks from 2017 to 2020, found that board composition has a positive, strong, and significant impact on firm performance as measured by return on assets. These consistent findings imply that boards with a greater proportion of outside directors tend to achieve superior performance.

In contrast, various studies conducted in Nigeria (Uwuigbe, 2015; Ogbulu and Emeni, 2018; Garba and Abubakar, 2018) as well as a non-Nigerian study (Guest, 2019) have indicated that the representation of independent non-executive directors on corporate boards is inversely related to firm performance. Mangena et al. (2019), utilizing a sample of 157 listed firms in Zimbabwe from 2010 to 2016, discovered that the proportion of non-executive directors significantly correlates negatively with firm performance as measured by Tobin's Q.

Nwanne and Okonkwo (2019) examined the relationship between corporate board characteristics and the performance of Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria during the period from 2008 to 2017. This investigation was prompted by investor skepticism in the capital market, ongoing agency issues, and the insolvency challenges faced by major firms, including banks. The primary aim was to analyze the impact of corporate board attributes on the financial performance of DMBs in Nigeria. Four research models or hypotheses were developed based on the reviewed literature, focusing on key factors influencing the performance of DMBs within the Nigerian banking sector. The study concentrated on three quoted DMBs, employing a Judgmental Sampling Technique over a decade, specifically from 2008 to 2017. The study's population consisted of 21 DMBs listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. Data analysis was conducted using econometric software E-Views, with a random effects model applied to the panel data. The findings revealed a positive and significant relationship between board skills and annual profits, among other factors.

Board Independence and Profitability

Edaet (2018) conducted a study examining the relationship between corporate governance, return on assets (ROA), and executive compensation within financial firms in Indonesia. The research sample comprised 13 companies listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange from 2010 to 2016. The findings revealed a positive correlation between executive compensation, executive independence, and ROA.

This relationship is attributed to the fact that the bonuses awarded to executives are contingent upon the company's profitability; thus, higher profits lead to increased bonuses for executives. Additionally, the study indicated that the corporate governance mechanism, specifically executive independence, serves to moderate the relationship between executive compensation and performance.

Crownwell (2020) explored the relationship between corporate governance and the financial value of a sample of 150 companies listed on Bursa Malaysia from 2016 to 2019. Utilizing a panel-based regression model, the study assessed various variables, with ROA and Tobin's Q as the dependent variables. The independent variables included board independence, company size, leverage, directors' remuneration, board size, and auditors. The results demonstrated that company size had a positive and highly significant relationship with ROA, while leverage exhibited a negative yet significant impact on financial performance (ROA). Furthermore, a positive and significant relationship was found between board independence and company value.

Fuzi, AbdulHalim, and Julizaerma (2018) conducted a study on the relationship between Board Independence and return on assets. The research focused on selected publicly listed companies in Iran during the period from 2014 to 2017. Utilizing regression analysis, the results indicated a varied relationship between the proportion of independent directors and return on assets. Despite some companies having a higher number of independent directors, this did not necessarily lead to an improvement in return on assets. Therefore, it is essential to monitor the presence of independent directors on the board to enhance shareholder value.

Okolie and Uwejeyan (2022) investigated the financial performance and corporate board characteristics within Nigerian conglomerates. The study categorized board attributes into several components: Board Meetings, Board Committees, Board Size, Board Shareholdings, and Board Independence, with Return on Assets (ROA) serving as the measure of financial performance. The results indicated that board shareholdings and board size positively influenced financial performance, while board independence also had a significant impact. Additionally, the audit committee was found to affect the financial performance of Nigerian conglomerates. However, board meetings did not demonstrate a significant effect on financial performance. In light of these findings, the study advocated for a robust collaboration between board members and shareholders to ensure accountability, transparency, and teamwork, while also emphasizing the importance of maintaining board independence to enhance the financial performance of conglomerates in Nigeria.

Gap in Literature

The examination of prior empirical studies revealed that a significant number of these investigations were conducted in countries such as Iran, Malaysia, Indonesia, Zimbabwe, and the United States, with very few studies taking place in Nigeria. This represents a notable gap that the current study seeks to address, thereby alleviating the scarcity of research on this topic within the Nigerian context. Additionally, it was noted that most research focused on sectors like banking (specifically Deposit

Money Banks), the public sector, finance, and conglomerates, while there was a lack of studies pertaining to the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. This research aims to bridge that gap.

Theoretical Underpinning

This study is anchored on agency theory. Agency theory was proposed by Jensen and Meckling in 1976. This theory posits that the board of directors serves as a crucial internal governance mechanism within a company (Ogbechie and Koufopoulos, 2019). However, the board's effectiveness in overseeing and regulating activities diminishes when internal members, such as executives or others closely associated with management, constitute the majority of the board. Proponents of corporate governance contend that board oversight is more effective when the majority of directors are independent outsiders and when there is an increase in shareholdings among directors (Kren & Kerr, 2018). Importantly, non-executive directors are regarded as vital long-term and impartial decision-makers who monitor the governance process. From a corporate governance standpoint, their independence from management and any potential conflicts of interest enhance their role as a reliable control mechanism, enabling them to focus on maximizing shareholder value (Beasley, 2019).

Typical examples of agency relationships include the dynamics between employers and employees, as well as between shareholders (the principals) and the CEO. Agency theory highlights the inherent conflict between self-serving managers and the owners, where managers wield control over the firm while owners experience the majority of the financial consequences. The original model by Jensen and Meckling (1976) illustrates this conflict by demonstrating that lower stakes for managers result in increased non-pecuniary expenditures, as they do not fully account for the associated costs.

METHODOLOGY

This research employed a longitudinal design. Typically, the same manufacturing firms assessed at Time 1 were also evaluated at Time 2, and so forth. The study population consisted of sixty (60) publicly listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria, encompassing sectors such as industrials, basic materials, consumer goods, and oil and gas, as of December 31, 2022. The research employed panel data to facilitate an analysis that spans both temporal and spatial dimensions. The sample comprised various sectors, including industrials, basic materials, consumer goods, and oil and gas. Secondary data was gathered from the corporate annual reports of manufacturing firms over a ten-year period, specifically from 2013 to 2022. The study will focus on annual financial reports due to their voluntary availability, convenience, and enhanced potential for result comparability. Additionally, these reports are generated annually and made accessible to the public. Another rationale for utilizing corporate annual reports as a data source is that many stakeholders rely on published audited annual reports as their primary information source (Emuze, Dabor & Atu, 2019).

Data analysis Method

The data set was analyzed utilizing both descriptive and inferential statistics. This indicates that the study aimed to evaluate the data to derive the mean, standard deviation, and additional outcomes from

the descriptive analysis. Furthermore, the research included a correlation matrix analysis, diagnostic statistical analysis, serial correlation analysis, constant residual error assessment, model misspecification evaluation, and the Hausman test. The hypothesis was tested using the Panel Least Squares (Random Effect) method.

Model Specification

The model for the study is premised on the main objective and anchored on the sub-objective. The study modified the work of Niresh and Velnampy (2019), the model explicitly is presented below:

Return on Asset = $f(\text{board attributes})$

$$\text{ROA} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{BDVTY} + \beta_2 \text{BCOM} + \beta_3 \text{BINDP} + \text{LEV} + \mu$$

Where:

β_0 = constant;

$\beta_1 - \beta_5$ = Represented the regression coefficients of the slope of the variables in the model.

μ = error term

it = Represented time and cross-sections.

BDVTY = Board diversity (women directors) (Independent variable)

BCOM = Board committee (Independent variable)

BINDP = Board independence (Independent variable)

ROA = Return on Asset (Dependent variable)

LEV = Leverage

Apriori Expectation

The research proposed that the Board Executive Director will have a negative effect on profitability measured by return on asset. This is same with Board non-executive directors and Board committee while Board diversity (women directors) and board independence is proposed to have a positive effect with profitability measured with return on asset. This position was as a result of the results of previous empirical work.

Table 1: Operationalization of Variables

1. Dependent Variables	Descripti on	Measurement	Author	Hypothesis Number	Apriori Expectati on
Profitability	ROA	ROA is measured by dividing a firm's net income by the average of its total assets.	Wetukha (2020)		
2. Independent Variable					
Board diversity (women directors)	BDVTY	This is the proportion of female directors to the total number of Directors .	Lin, Luo, and Tang (2019)	Ho ₃	+
Board committee	BCOM	Total number of directors on the board.	Ongore, K'obonyo, Ogutu and Bosire (2019)	Ho ₄	-
board independence	BINDP	Measured using a dummy variable stating 1 if the board members are all non-executive directors that were appointed at the AGM in each accounting period and 0 for otherwise	Nakano and Nguyen (2019),	Ho ₅	+
3. Control Variable					
Leverage	LEV	Total book value of debt/Total assets	Oyedokun (2019)		

Source: Researcher’s Compilation, (2024).

Data Analysis and Presentation

Descriptive Statistics

The data used for the analyses were presented in Appendix 1 of this study while the descriptive statistics is presented below.

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Std. Dev
ROA	0.2057	0.0246	0.4967	0.0820
BDVTY	0.4180	0.0400	22.2222	1.9999
BCOM	13.2033	7.0000	20.0000	3.1142
BINDP	0.0500	0.0000	1.0000	0.2181
LEV	13.0421	10.1100	68.2100	12.7151

Source: Author’s computation, 2024

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics for the variables utilized in the study. The average return on assets (ROA) was recorded at 0.2057, with the lowest and highest values being 0.0246 and 0.4967, respectively. The standard deviation of ROA was 0.0820, indicating a significant concentration around the mean. The means for the independent variables BDVTY, BCOM, and BINDP were 0.4180, 13.2033, and 0.0500, respectively. The standard deviations of these independent variables showed notable clustering around their means, with the exceptions of BDVTY and BINDP. The control variable LEV had a mean of 13.0421 and a standard deviation of 12.7151.

Correlation Matrix

Table

Correlation Matrix

	ROA	BEXD	BNED	BDVTY	BCOM	BINDP	LEV
ROA	1.000						
BDVTY	-0.0292	-0.0605	0.3210	1.000			
BCOM	0.0442	0.1116	0.3443	0.2012	1.0000		
BINDP	0.0823	0.9087	-0.0087	-0.0252	0.0985	1.000	
LEV	-0.0672	-0.0165	-0.0164	-0.0199	-0.1458	-0.0257	1.000

Source: Author’s computation, 2024

The correlation matrix presented in Table 3 indicates that the variables demonstrate both positive and negative relationships. This is evident in the correlation between BEXD and ROA (0.0088). The strength of the associations among the variables remained below the critical threshold of 0.80, implying that multicollinearity is not a concern among the predictor variables (Studenmund, 2014). To further confirm the accuracy of these findings, a Variance Inflation Factor test was conducted.

Diagnostics test

Diagnostics test was conducted in order to fulfil the assumptions of regression. Some of the diagnostics test we did was autocorrelation test, serial correlations test, constant residual error (Heteroskedasticity), multicollinearity, Ramsey, Husman, normality and model misspecification test. All the test conducted yielded positive results.

Multivariate Analyses and Panel Least Squares (Random Effect)

In addition to estimating the study's model using the panel least squares estimation technique, a Hausman test was conducted to assess the specification of effects. The hypotheses of the study were evaluated at a significance level of 5%, meaning that if the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected; otherwise, it is not rejected.

Table 4: Hausman Test

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test			
Test cross-section random effects			
Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	8.7231	7	0.2731

Source: Authors' Computation, 2024

The table presented above displays the outcome of the Hausman test, with $HM(7) = 8.7231$ and a p-value of 0.2731, which is greater than 0.05. Based on this finding, we disregarded the fixed effect model at the 5% significance level and consequently accepted the random effect model for the panel least squares regression results.

Table 5: Inferential Statistics –Panel Least Squares (Random Effect)

Variables	Dependent variable: ROA			
	Fixed Effect			
	B	S.E	t-Stat.	Prob.
Constant	0.1836	0.0102	17.8820	0.0000
BDVTY	1.7406	0.7006	2.4844	0.0108
BCOM	0.0074	0.0106	0.6942	0.4879
BINDP	-0.1209	0.1158	-19.211	-0.3016
LEV	0.0215	0.0314	0.6833	0.4948
R-squared		0.6719		
Adjusted R-squared		0.5870		

Durbin-Watson stat		1.9322		
S.E.		0.0787		
F-statistics		5.6163		
Prob. (F-statistics)		0.0001* *		

**significant at 5 per cent level

Source: Authors' Computation, 2024

Table 5 presents the findings from the panel least squares regression analysis conducted for this study's model. The explanatory variables utilized significantly elucidate the relationship between board characteristics and the return on assets of publicly listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. This conclusion is supported by the results of the random effects panel least squares regression, with F-statistics recorded at 5.6163 and a p-value of 0.0001, which is less than the 0.05 threshold. Additionally, the adjusted R-squared value was determined to be 0.5870, indicating that approximately 58.70% of the systematic variation in the dependent variable (financial performance) can be attributed to the explanatory variables employed in this study. Conversely, around 41.3% of the variations are attributed to other factors not included in the model, which were effectively accounted for by the standard error of the regression, SE = 0.0787.

Test of Hypotheses

We tested our hypotheses at 5% level of significance (that is, if p-value < 0.05 reject Ho, else do otherwise).

H₀₁. The presence of female directors on corporate boards does not have a significant impact on the profitability of publicly listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. However, as indicated in Table 4.8, our analysis reveals that board gender diversity, specifically the inclusion of female directors, does indeed exert a positive and statistically significant influence on the profitability of these companies, with a coefficient of $\beta_1 = 1.7406$; SE = 0.7006, and a p-value of 0.0108, which is less than the 0.05 threshold. Consequently, this finding leads us to reject the null hypothesis posited in the study, which asserted that board gender diversity (female directors) does not have a significant positive effect on the profitability of publicly listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

H₀₂. The analysis indicates that the presence of a board committee does not have a significant impact on the profitability of publicly listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. As shown in Table 4.8, the findings reveal that the coefficient for the board committee is $\beta_1 = 0.0074$, with a standard error of SE = 0.0106 and a p-value of 0.4879, which exceeds the 0.05 threshold. Consequently, the null hypothesis posited

in this study—that the board committee does not significantly influence the profitability of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria—remains unchallenged.

H₀₃. The independence of the board does not have a substantial impact on the profitability of publicly listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The findings presented in Table 4.8 indicate that board independence has a negative and statistically significant effect on the profitability of these companies, with a coefficient of $\beta_1 = -0.1209$; SE = 0.1158, and a p-value of -0.3016, which is less than 0.05. Consequently, this leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis proposed in the study, which posited that board independence does not significantly influence the profitability of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The primary aim of this research is to explore the relationship between board characteristics and the profitability of publicly listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The specific aims of the study include assessing the impact of executive directors on the profitability of these companies; evaluating the influence of non-executive directors on profitability; analyzing the effect of gender diversity on boards, particularly the presence of female directors, on profitability; investigating the role of board committees in relation to profitability; and examining the effect of board independence on the profitability of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

The study revealed that the presence of female directors on corporate boards positively and significantly influences the profitability of publicly listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. This outcome aligns with the research conducted by Adams & Ferreira (2019), Campbell and Mingués-Vera (2018), and Farrell and Hersch (2016), which indicates that female board members can enhance both firm value and market valuation. Conversely, Rose (2017) indicates that there is no significant correlation between female board representation and return on assets.

Furthermore, the research indicated that board committees do not have a significant impact on the profitability of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria. This finding contradicts the studies by Connelly & Limpaphayom (2019) and Shakir (2018), which demonstrate a positive relationship between board characteristics and firms' return on assets.

Finally, the study found that board independence negatively and significantly affects the profitability of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. This conclusion is at odds with the findings of Edaet (2018), Crownwell (2020), and Fuzi, AbdulHalim, and Julizaerma (2018), who reported a positive association between board independence and firms' return on assets.

Summary of Findings

The research examined the correlation between board characteristics and the profitability of publicly listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria, with the findings summarized as follows: The presence of an executive director on the board does not have a significant impact on the profitability of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

- i) The inclusion of female directors on the board positively and significantly influences the profitability of publicly listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.
- ii) The establishment of board committees does not significantly affect the profitability of publicly listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.
- iii) Board independence exerts a negative and significant influence on the profitability of publicly listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Conclusion

This study investigated the relationship between board characteristics and the profitability of publicly listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The results indicate that board attributes, such as gender diversity among directors and the level of board independence, significantly influence the profitability of these companies.

Recommendations

According to the findings of this study, we propose the following recommendations:

1. The inclusion of female directors should be enhanced to bolster the financial performance of companies.
2. The ratio of Executive Directors compared to Non-executive directors should be enhanced to reduce Board Independence which has negative impact on financial performance of manufacturing firms.
3. Government should come up regulation on manufacturing companies to reduce the number of board committees to ensure that the board fulfils its responsibility of growing their firms financially.

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